

1 Systems biologic identification of genes that support or antagonize the tumor life cycle by controlling tumor
2 evolution and enriched or depleted in clonal selection for more effective management of resistance and
3 recurrence.

4 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

5 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

6 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

7 East Islip, NY USA 11730

8 A fundamental block in the ability to (completely) clinically manage cancer as a disease (at any stage, at
9 initial presentation and in recurrence or resistance) stems from two main processes: an unparalleled rate
10 of evolution (selection pressure at the clonal level, in a population of single tumor cells) resulting from
11 genomic instability inherent to loss of tumor suppression, which is coupled to a second essential feature of
12 transformation, the speed of cell cycle completion following effective transformation.

13 Selection generated by cooperative pressure resulting from high cell cycle speed and the number of
14 changes able to be blindly sampled through enhancement of mutagenic functions results in effective
15 sampling of alternative cellular states through optimization of the tumor transcriptome. Thus, genomic
16 instability will be a defining component of the essential properties of the tumor cell at the clonal level that
17 enable continual challenge to human clinical interventions and include active processes, which can
18 mediated by modulation of systems manipulating the genome at the base pair level (e.g., base pair
19 deamination through regulation of enzymes like AICDA and APOBEC) or be proxy resulting from inability
20 to maintain fidelity of the genome due to replication stress caused by the speed of the cell cycle, as well as
21 other failures to maintain genomic integrity like impairment of DNA repair pathways, and other more
22 karyotypic or structurally based processes that are a characteristic property of the genomic stability
23 during clonal selection and in the tumor, like chromosomal rearrangement events.

24 An example of the importance of genomic stability in transformation is illustrated by study of tumor
25 suppressive function of MLH/MSH mismatch repair pathways (like transformation enhancing properties of
26 germline mismatch repair mutations in MLH enzymes in MMR pathway, or the bona fide tumor suppressor
27 function of MSH2 that appear functionally similar to p53 in sufficiency to effectively transform a cell
28 evidenced by induction of tumor cell marker expression [ECT2 and others] following genetic depletion of
the gene).

The level of sophistication associated with the selection pressure of the cancer cells existing within any
tumor should not be underestimated, as it includes considerations of the cancer cell at a greater level as
an organism, evidenced in the enrichment of genes that function in immune system (tumor surveillance).
Enrichment of the immune system observed in genes that support tumor evolution (genes that are most
effective at the transcriptome level in supporting selection pressure to drive evolution of the tumor: genes
that correlate with tumor size, genes that are enriched in tumors that effectively metastasize to distant
organ site within the host, or genes that are expressed most differently in the tumor when comparing a
measure that can be reasonably believed to be a factor the tumor is able to appreciate when organizing a
strategy that optimizes selection pressure considerations that are cell autonomous, intrinsic to the tumor
cell, considerations that involve a second degree of sophistication: this second "level" of calculations
executed by the tumor cell during clonal selection consider measures that are more complex than effective
completion of the cell cycle or silencing of cell death pathways.

These evolutionary strategies in contrast enhance selection by limiting host tumor defense and function by
altering the tumor cell transcriptome to antagonize a cell-extrinsic function of the host that will challenge
the tumor life cycle: at the cell surface of the tumor clone to impair immune recognition, or by altering the
soluble immune effector profile of the tumor microenvironment to antagonize tumor infiltrating cells by
activating exhaustion of by other senescence inducing behaviors. Changes at the clonal level that promote
survival of the tumor as a organism but through changes at the clonal level effectively promote the overall

1 tumor life cycle but at the level of the gene as a collection of changes in a clone. These changes effected
2 through processes that utilize mutagenic or genomic instability based mechanisms can be reasonably
3 expected, given the number of genes within the transcriptome and time scale of selection during
4 transformation, to consider (whether actively by some intelligent mechanism or otherwise passively)
5 survival of the tumor as a collection of individual cells, and other life cycle orientated consideration like
6 survival upon dissemination in a secondary environment within the host, where selection can be observed
7 to favor changes in the tumor cell transcriptome that optimize dissemination (metastasis), orchestrating
8 chronologically separated (i.e., a gene that has the ability to promote selection of the tumor, functioning at
9 a clonal level while optimizing selection with an evolutionary time scale of greater than one cell division), a
10 set of changes that alone or as a collection are anticipated to promote dissemination, and include
11 supporting immune evasion, not in the primary TME or at the surface of the clone within the primary tumor
12 but at a separate organ site, through means that anticipate organ specific immunologic activity or by a
13 second more speculative but still evidence based mechanism, to function at the clonal level during
14 selection but later at distant organ site by an identity-based mechanism that promotes mimicry by
15 completion of a minimal number of changes in the tumor cell transcriptome that in composite are able to
16 support tumor survival as an organism operating within a foreign host, and as a life cycle.

17 The sophistication level here that can be expected, an essential basis of failure of human clinical
18 interventions in any patient death of recurrence, thus assumes a level of intelligence of undefined nature
19 or source that indicates the ability to enact a combination of transcriptional changes whose overall
20 selective benefit are then greater than those that can result from a rapid collection of cell cycle divisions
21 coupled with mutagenic sampling of the transcriptome at random. The complex nature of the selective
22 pressure that is required here includes measures that enhance survival of the clone by in the context of
23 the tumor life cycle. These changes derive their survival benefit by enhancing effective completion of the
24 life cycle at a time scale that is by definition of different nature. This complex selective pressure reflect a
25 strategy that effectively balances survival upon one cell cycle completion and survival of the cancer
26 months or years later.

27 The need to select only those changes that will promote survival at the following cell division, a pure
28 selective pressure mechanism of the cancer cell clone, with the demands of selecting changes that
anticipate survival benefit much later in the life cycle of the tumor as an organism at a chronologically
separate time point, reflects highly intelligent and efficient means, an ability to manage demands of the
tumor early in its life following transformation to promote robust primary tumor growth with considerations
that reflect considerations of transcriptional properties of a distant organ site. Thus, effective clinical
interventions that will completely and successfully prohibit tumor surgical must anticipate the number of
changes and nature of selection strategies that can be difficult to discern, that as a composite strategy
include a large number of individual efforts that challenge clinical intervention at presentation, at
completion of therapy in resistance disease, or at recurrence.

This third measure that identifies transcriptional changes that support clonal evolution is a comparison of
tumor transcriptome based on the number of days the host survives following diagnosis (for example, less
than 100 days or greater than 1000 days). The survival of the host can be expected to reflect the overall
effectiveness of selective pressure, and described efforts as an aggregate that identify the ability of the
tumor to effectively challenge the host during the course of the tumor life cycle. This host survival based
method to identify genes that function in tumor evolution by enhancement of selection pressure display
significant enrichment of molecules that function in tumor defense, and suggest a cognizant effort by the
tumor but at the clonal level operating within a host by antagonizing the host by selecting against functions
of a system that is specialized in elimination of transformed cells. Since a rapid host death is an overall
indication the tumor transcriptome is enriched in changes that promote survival by enhancement of
selection pressure, the genes identified here are important for understanding ways in which disease in
humans can be managed throughout the course of the illness, and include genes that function in
recruitment of natural killer cells, changes in class I and class II MHC receptor repertoire and antigen
presenting, those at the tumor cell surface that antagonize host efforts to mark the tumor as non-self and
involve cell types not restricted to the killer cell like the gamma delta T cell that uses multiple means
(engaging MR1, MICA/B, CD1 co-receptor help, and tumor surveillance assistance in immune cell/tumor
engagement through immunoglobulin-like receptors like VISTA) to conduct tumor surveillance, as well as

1 changes in cytokine, chemokine other immune effectors like soluble interferon types whose silencing or
2 activation block successful clinical management of disease by antagonizing cytotoxic responses by CD8+
3 lymphocytes through even separate mechanisms, like local activation of exhaustion programs in tumor
4 infiltrating immune cells and includes highly selected for changes in expression of genes that interfere with
5 self non-self discrimination through changes in Ly lymphocyte antigen profiles).

6 Thus, tumor evolution, despite our ability to simplify and define clonal evolution as a simple function of two
7 defining elements of the cancer cell: cooperation between 1. rapid cell cycle speed of transformed cells
8 and the 2. mutagenic nature of the selection process, the major means currently understood to function in
9 clonal evolution (gene expression changes resulting from promotion of genomic instability and modulation
10 of repair and mutagenic processes, intrinsic features of the tumor), when identified as individual
11 components, by whole transcriptome discovery of the selection events that most significantly influenced
12 tumor evolution, are reflective of a more complex selective strategy comprised of cell intrinsic and cell
13 extrinsic considerations, that include evolution at disparate time scales through interference with multiple
14 organ systems and cellular program in the human. Despite evidence that suggests a greater
15 sophistication or intelligence level in this evolutionary process, future efforts to improve medical
16 interventions in the treatment of cancer can be reasonably achieved, as each gene whose expression was
17 selected for can be identified, and its relative contribution to selection can be estimated through degree of
18 differential expression and study of separate discovery sets (size versus stage versus survival at the
19 transcriptome level of the tumor), the identity of the gene and estimated biological relevance to disease
20 (which has some usefulness as a partial correlate of ability of the selection events to antagonize a clinical
21 intervention) will support clinical management of cancer as a disease by enabling therapeutic target
22 discovery for drug development for clinical management of cancer in a more effective manner.

23 Systems biologic study of the tumor life cycle for identification of genes and pathways that influence tumor
24 evolution describe how cancers achieve resistant behavior, regardless of suggested sophistication in
25 selection and will support current and ongoing discovery research for therapeutic target development to
26 address, quantitatively and comprehensively, each of the strategies that support resistant behavior by
27 cancers by identifying each of the genes in the transcriptome whose selection has been enriched for or
28 against in a systematic fashion.